

Language Conundrum in India: Way Forward

- *A Case for the Promotion of Mother Tongues, Local Languages, and the Formal Adoption of Hindi and Sanskrit as the National Languages of Resurgent “Vishwaguru” Bharat*

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Abstract: A nation’s national language is an indicator of its identity and uniqueness. Unfortunately, for various reasons, India as a country could not come to a consensus on adopting Hindi as its national language. The internal conflicting opinions have benefited foreign languages and associated countries in numerous ways. This can be validated when we look at the interest of natives of other countries—authors, bureaucrats, and politicians—in India’s National Language issues. This research article examines the importance of promoting the mother tongue, local languages, and the adoption of the national language in letter and spirit in India. Recognising the linguistic diversity in the country, the study argues for a comprehensive approach that emphasises the preservation and promotion of mother tongue, regional, and local languages while also giving due recognition to Hindi and Sanskrit as the national languages. This paper emphasises the cultural, social, and emotional significance of the mother tongue and local languages in preserving the unique identities and heritage of different communities across India. It also highlights the historical and spiritual value of Sanskrit, as well as its contributions to Indian literature, philosophy, and ancient scriptures. By advocating for the promotion and preservation of mother tongues, and local languages, and the adoption of Hindi and Sanskrit as the national languages, this research aims to acknowledge and celebrate the linguistic diversity of India while upholding the importance of a unifying language or languages. Incorporating all these languages on the lines of NEP-2020 would foster a sense of belongingness, inclusivity, and cultural pride, strengthening the social fabric of the nation.

Keywords: Local languages; Indigenous Culture; Mother Tongue; Sanskrit: India’s National Language; Language Politics in India; Hindi Diwas; NEP2020; Bharat – Vishwaguru

Introduction

Language helps individuals communicate their thoughts and understand the cultures of different people. Human language is rooted in communication, teaching, and learning. Language has been playing a vital role in shaping social contacts and knowledgeability since the dawn of civilization. It became a tool for people to convey their thoughts and preserve their culture. Language has been used as a vehicle to make smooth social contacts with other members of society. In addition, it holds pivotal importance in creating a flourishing society by helping different groups understand each other’s social preferences and other cues. Our society is heavily dependent on language to create relationships, and it remains an indispensable tool for understanding, communicating, and creating relationships within our society. Furthermore, it allows humans to store their knowledge in a way that speakers can understand it better. The study is presented in four sections with subsections to accommodate discussion on linguistic concerns, importance of mother tongue and regional languages; and the advantages of having national language/s for India, India is the largest Democracy in the world.

Section-I

A. An Overview of Linguistic Conundrum in India

India is commonly recognised as a single geographical unit, but, throughout ancient times, India has never constituted a politically unified state. Under British rule, India's provinces were not demarcated in any specific manner, but a systematic division of the provinces was crucial after independence. Language has been the most contentious topic in both the pre- and post-Independence eras. If we consider Indian independence, then the linguistic issue has existed since the time of the British. Lord Macaulay suggested that English become the primary language to study. In 1835, the recommendation was made. Therefore, everybody who applied for government service at the time was expected to study English. At the time the Indian Constitution was drafted, Mahatma Gandhi advocated for the creation of Hindi as an official language. He favoured adopting only one language as the medium of instruction. However, leaders like Ram Manohar Lohiya opposed this notion and advocated for the adoption of other subjective preferences.

When the issue of the reorganisation of states on the basis of language reached its peak, to examine this issue, the government appointed several commissions. In 1948, the Dhar Committee, under the supervision of S.K. Dhar, a judge of the Allahabad High Court, was constituted, but this commission favoured the reorganisation of states on the basis of administrative convenience. Likewise, the JVP (Jawaharlal Nehru, Vallabhbhai Patel, and Pattabhi Sitaramayya) committee appointed by Congress in December 1948 also dismissed the linguistic issue. In 1953, as a result of Nehru's statement in the parliament regarding the formation of states, another commission was formed, known as the State Reorganisation Commission. The Commission consisted of three members: Justice Fazal Ali, Dr. H.N. Kunzru, and Dr. K.N. Pennikar. It was an independent Commission and was empowered to report on boundary issues for the whole country. Under the State Reorganisations Act, 1956, the government formed 14 states and six union territories on a linguistic basis. This linguistic diversity was accommodated while addressing the systematic state reorganisation concern for administrative reasons. Thus, states were reorganised with linguistic attribution besides geographical and administrative factors, in addition to economic reasons. The linguistic reorganisation of the states resolved the problem at that time. It did not affect the federal structure of the nation or weaken the centre. Some scholars even argue that the formation of the states on the basis of language was the only possible way to maintain national unity. However, the linguistic reorganisation of Indian states could not resolve all the problems related to linguistic conflicts or disputes over boundaries. As demands for separate states are heard even today, even within the states that were formed on the basis of language.

B. Multilingualism: Advantages and threats

Multilingualism refers to the existence and popularity of many languages. Knowledge of multiple languages is a great advantage for individuals. They will be able to learn about their respective language cultures, which empowers them to better understand and connect with people from different parts of the world. Thus, a polyglot has an edge over others in today's society. Especially when one travels to foreign countries, knowledge of the language of that particular country can be very useful. Thus, multilingualism helps individuals live in a world without hassles over basic survival necessities. Nevertheless, there are many disadvantages if a foreign language or one foreign and one native language, or bilingual practise, is adopted as a policy while recognising a national language. We are witnesses to the craze for European languages that has become a threat to our native languages. There are many instances where the adopted practise of speaking two languages, mostly English and their native language, has caused bilingual children to lose their native language as they are encouraged to only speak English more than their mother tongue. Parents and teachers must encourage the practise of promoting the local language, their mother tongue, so that the important links between them and their family and other community members are not lost. Encouraging parents to maintain their child's first language or mother tongue is key in order for the child to benefit from being a member of society. It also helps to create a sense of unity between native-language communities. For example, the United States is home to over 350 different languages, according to the US Census Bureau, but English is the most widely spoken language. The importance of a national language lies in its ability to prepare parents and their children for most governmental functions and allow them to communicate more effectively with their peers. Parents can then pass on the indigenous knowledge of their culture and heritage, which will enrich the lives of their children.

C. Language Politics Depriving Hindi the status of National Language in India

This sub-section discusses the controversies and conflicts related to Hindi as the national language of India. On September 14, 1949, Hindi was declared the official language of the Union of India. Later, When the Constitution of India was adopted in 1950, Article 343(1) of the Indian Constitution specifically mentions that "The official language of the Union shall be Hindi in Devanagari script. Article 343(1) of the Indian Constitution specifically mentions that "The official language of the Union shall be Hindi in Devanagari script". English, in addition to Hindi, is recognised as an official language of India. Different Indian states establish their own official languages through legislation. It also stated that English would be phased out in favour of Hindi over a period of 15 years.

Hindi is the mother tongue of 180 million people and the second language of 300 million more. Hindi is renowned as the "Language of Unity" because Mahatma Gandhi used it to unify India. The inclusion of the Hindi term "Swadeshi" in the Oxford Dictionary is a historic event and a source of tremendous pride. Introducing Hindi to a worldwide audience

has not been a simple undertaking, and keeping the language's importance in mind, former US President George Bush set aside \$114 million to make Hindi a part of the school curriculum to be taught from kindergarten to graduate level. In addition to that, numerous Hindi terms, such as Guru, Nirvana, Roti, and Adda, are accepted and understood worldwide. In spite of solid ground to support Hindi as the National language, as non-Hindi-speaking parts of India, such as South India (whose languages are not even closely comparable to Hindi), were not pleased with this decision, Parliament passed the Official Languages Act of 1963, which authorised the use of English and Hindi for official purposes after 1965. It is unimaginable that English is the official language of certain Northeastern states, including Arunachal Pradesh and Nagaland.

Hindi is a member of the Indo-Aryan branch of the Indo-European language family. Later, Persian impacted Hindi, and the Mughals added their own changes to the language along the way. Despite the fact that Hindi developed from Sanskrit, many of its words have Arabic or Persian origins. Hindi is often known as a "link language" since it has brought together the enormous Indian Diaspora living all over the world and bridged the divide between North and South India. Hindi has spread over the world and is now spoken not just in India but also in Mauritius, Surinam, Trinidad & Tobago, South Africa, and New Zealand.

Hindi is also becoming adopted in South India, a region of the country that was once resistant to accepting Hindi as a national language. Deve Gowda, the former Chief Minister of Karnataka, spoke out in 1997 in support of Hindi promotion; later, Karunanidhi, the former Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu, recited a poem in Hindi during a campaign; and Jayalalitha (the current Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu) also campaigned in Hindi in support of Hindi promotion. (NP) On September 14, 1949, the Constituent Assembly of India decided by one vote that Hindi would be the official language of India. To mark this august occasion, Hindi Diwas is celebrated every year on September 14. Hindi Diwas is celebrated across the country. This day is marked by many schools, institutions, and organisations by hosting various events and competitions such as poetry recitation, elocution, storytelling, essay writing, and Hindi vocabulary quizzes. World Hindi Day (Vishwa Hindi Diwas) is celebrated on January 10th every year in several countries, including India, Nepal, Mauritius, Suriname, Guyana, Trinidad and Tobago, and South Africa. (ToI NP) Language politics in India have been a long-standing issue, though Hindi has long been the language prescribed as the national language owing to socio-political factors. Appeasement policies are an easy bait to lure citizens during elections. Due to this, the political parties blow the matter up and harp on the strings of sentiments.

D. Scope for Sanskrit as India's National Language

National Language Controversy as a National Loss Language politics in India is a complex issue, as English is assumed to be the language of the elite. History is witness to the fact that when there are internal differences, only outsiders derive benefits. The same is true with regard to the national language controversy in India. Nevertheless, if India considers adopting Sanskrit, the classical language that is mother to thousands of languages spread across the world, as its national language, it has immense potential to benefit the country in various ways.

- If Sanskrit is adopted as India's National Language, foreign students, scholars, and students will have to acquire proficiency for various professional and bureaucratic reasons. This will add to the creation of vast opportunities with long-term potential.
- Over a period of time, the money that is spent on procuring books authored in various foreign languages can be saved by promoting indigenous publishers of Indian National and regional Languages.
- Along with Sanskrit, the other local languages like Hindi, Tamil, Gujarati, Marathi, Telugu, etc. will strengthen regionally.
- Adoption of Sanskrit will be a mark of National pride, projecting the true spirit of "Unity in Diversity."
- There are scientifically proven advantages to reciting Sanskrit hymns and verses.
- The Sanskrit language has similarities in vocabulary and grammar with the Latin and Greek languages. So, a learner with proficiency in Sanskrit will find it easier to learn foreign languages.
- There are many South Asian countries where Sanskrit occupies an important place. India, the only country with Sanskrit as the national language, will have a major role to play in terms of sharing knowledge and intellectual capital.

Section-II

A. Significance of Mother Tongue

International Mother Language Day is observed annually on February 21. In response to a proposal from Bangladesh, the UNESCO General Conference established it in 1999. The Day is an essential platform to promote the importance of cultural and linguistic diversity and multilingualism for peaceful and sustainable societies. UNESCO has been a leader in promoting mother-tongue-based multilingual education from the earliest years of instruction. Education in the maternal tongue is a crucial factor for inclusion and high-quality learning, and it also enhances learning outcomes and academic performance, according to research. This is essential, particularly in elementary education, to prevent

knowledge gaps and accelerate learning and comprehension. Moreover, a multilingual education founded on the mother tongue enables all students to completely participate in society. It promotes mutual comprehension and respect and contributes to the preservation of the rich cultural and traditional heritage inherent in every language on earth. However, there is still a considerable distance to travel before ensuring that all students have access to education in their mother tongue. The majority of pupils in the majority of countries are taught in a language other than their native dialect, which hinders their ability to learn effectively.

Although there are many aspects that go into providing effective basic education, language is unquestionably the most important one for interaction and comprehension in the classroom. Despite the fact that the educational system in many emerging nations is still dominated by a single foreign language, these nations frequently exhibit both individual and social multilingualism. According to Skutnabb-Kangas (2000), instruction in a language that students do not speak is referred to as “submersion” since it is comparable to holding students under water without teaching them how to swim. Submersion makes both learning and teaching exceedingly challenging, especially when the language of instruction is also a second language for the teacher, compounded by ongoing challenges including low levels of teacher education, poorly planned, inadequate curriculum, and a lack of proper school facilities.

B. Mother tongue in Foundational Literacy and Primary Education

Mother-tongue-based bilingual teaching combines instructional content with the teaching of basic reading and writing skills in the learner’s first language, or L1. The use of the mother tongue, at least in the early years, in bilingual models and practises allows kids to develop comprehensive capabilities in addition to participating in the classroom. Bilingual models and practises vary, but what they all have in common is the use of the mother tongue. It is believed that using the mother tongue offers a myriad of positive impacts on education as it develops and encourages children’s expressiveness, activeness, and participation in learning (Berowa & Agbayani, 2019); it helps improve students’ academic skills (Cummins, 2000); it improves literacy and skills in the English language (Cummins, 2000); it also helps students gain higher academic achievement; it aids in the development of critical thinking; and above all, it enables stronger classroom participation. Linguists have argued that using the mother tongue in education is of great importance because it has the potential to produce proficient readers in a relatively short span, even for average or slow learners. Early childhood education and teaching are more easily understood when they are taught in a language that the students are already familiar with. Kids may communicate through writing as soon as they comprehend the principles of the orthographic (or other written) system of their language, and learning to read is most effective when kids are able to use psycholinguistic guessing techniques of the language. Submersion programmes, on the other hand, could be successful in teaching pupils to decipher words in the L2, but it might take them years before they understand the significance of what they are reading.

The significance of the mother tongue, or the language that a person learns from birth and uses most fluently, extends to various stages of an individual’s life. From infancy, a person begins to develop communication skills and verbal interactions primarily through their mother tongue. It is the language that expresses emotions, thoughts, and needs, establishing a strong sense of identity and belonging. Mother tongue allows individuals to connect with their family, community, and cultural heritage, fostering a deeper understanding of one’s roots.

Language is closely intertwined with cognitive development, particularly in early childhood. Research indicates that children learn most effectively when they are taught in their mother tongue. The familiarity of the language helps in comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and cognitive processing. The mother tongue enables individuals to express complex emotions, values, and cultural nuances more authentically. It carries a sense of cultural belonging, as it contains idioms, proverbs, and cultural references specific to a particular community. By maintaining and promoting the mother tongue, cultural traditions, folklore, and oral histories can be preserved and passed down to future generations. When individuals have a strong foundation in their mother tongue, they become more adaptable and open to learning new languages and cultural perspectives. One’s mother tongue also plays a crucial role in fostering inclusivity, especially in multicultural societies. It promotes a sense of cultural pride and encourages individuals from diverse linguistic backgrounds to maintain and celebrate their own languages. When mother tongues are valued and respected, it promotes intercultural dialogue, understanding, and social cohesion within a community or nation. Thus, Language is a medium of expression, and an individual should not be made to feel any less even if he or she knows just their mother tongue. By recognising, promoting, and preserving individuals’ mother tongues, we not only embrace linguistic diversity but also empower individuals to thrive personally, academically, and professionally.

C. Local/regional languages for Multilingualism through Linguistic Diversity

India is a linguistically diverse nation that boasts a multitude of regional and local languages. These languages play a crucial role in shaping the cultural fabric and societal framework of different regions across India. Recognising the importance of regional and local languages is essential to preserving cultural heritage, fostering a sense of identity, promoting multilingualism, and facilitating efficient communication and inclusivity among its citizens. One of the significant contributions of regional and local languages is their ability to preserve and promote the rich cultural heritage

of their respective communities. These languages act as vehicles for passing down customs, traditions, folklore, and historical knowledge unique to specific regions. Through regional languages, communities can express their cultural distinctiveness and ensure the continuity of age-old practises and rituals. For instance, languages like Kannada, Telugu, Urdu, and Malayalam have a strong connection to the arts, music, and literature, which have flourished over centuries (Singh, 2016). Preserving these languages is crucial for conserving India's diverse cultural heritage. Moreover, regional and local languages also play a pivotal role in fostering a sense of identity among individuals.

Language acts as a medium for individuals to express their emotions, values, and worldview. It serves as a powerful tool for connecting people to their roots and enabling them to understand their cultural context better. Speaking in one's mother tongue fosters a sense of belonging and pride, strengthening cultural identity and self-esteem. It allows individuals to fully express themselves and participate actively in their communities. Regional languages like Punjabi, Bengali, Tamil, and Gujarati not only serve as modes of communication but also serve as symbols of identity and cultural heritage (Rao, 2004). Upholding regional languages is, therefore, crucial for nurturing a harmonious and inclusive society. The importance of regional and local languages extends to facilitating inclusive development and effective communication. In India's vast and diverse landscape, not everyone is proficient in the commonly spoken languages such as Hindi or English. Using regional languages as a medium of instruction in schools, government offices, and public services facilitates more effective communication and helps bridge the linguistic and cultural gaps that exist (Behl, 2017). Many rural and tribal communities primarily communicate in their regional languages. Recognising and supporting these languages is essential for ensuring equal opportunities for all citizens. It allows individuals to participate fully in educational, economic, and social spheres, ensuring their voices are heard and their needs are met.

Section-III

A. National Language as a Cultural and Linguistic Unifying force

The national language serves as an identity factor for all the citizens of a particular country while also creating a sense of cultural and national pride. The importance of having a national language lies in its ability to give its citizens a sense of belonging, regardless of their number or level in government. A national language enables social interactions with others, providing oneness and blurring geographical boundaries. It serves as a unifying force for different cultures and languages, resonating the spirit of unity beyond diversity. A national language can also increase social benefits and have large-scale socio-economic implications. Speaking your first language can increase confidence as well as strengthen ties with family members, whereas fluency in a common language helps to strengthen networks and connections across national borders. It may not be an exaggeration to state the satirical treatment of Northern languages by their southern counterparts and vice versa. Chetan Bhagat's novels substantiate the aforementioned fact. Nevertheless, the reference is only to justify the importance of a national language. Such situations can be avoided by having one common language, i.e., a national language, that each citizen should honour and uphold, within or outside the country.

B. Sanskrit – the language of ‘Samskrta’

Origin of the Sanskrit language: Sanskrit is a highly esteemed language that has been used in many aspects of Indian culture, from religious texts to poetry. The Vedic version of Sanskrit emerged during the Vedic period and is considered to be the oldest form of the language. It was later refined into classical Sanskrit by renowned linguists like Panini. One of the greatest aspects of this language is its highly developed grammar, which was recorded by Panini in his “Astadhyayi”, the first Grammar book of Sanskrit, around the 4th century BCE. This text, along with other commentaries, is studied even today as one of the finest grammars ever written in any language. Sanskrit was also known as “Samskrta”, meaning ‘well-adorned’. The Vedas and Upanishads were two of the last sacred texts written in this language. Old Indo-Aryan languages are believed to be the oldest documents written in India and have been studied by several linguistic researchers for years.

Sanskrit, referred to as a liturgical language, is used in ceremonies and rituals in India and abroad by the followers of "Sanatan Dharm" and is a common language amongst all religions on the Indian subcontinent, such as Hinduism, Jainism, and Buddhism. This tradition kept it in high esteem among all modern Indians, even those living outside India. Sanskrit was the dominant classical language in ancient times in the greater Indian subcontinent and is believed to be the source for hundreds of other related languages. It also gave rise to a number of other languages and dialects spoken in India today. The ancestor language of all the Indo-Aryan languages is believed to be Proto-Indo-European, which is a family of Indo-European languages that have been spoken in the Indian subcontinent since ancient times. Thus, although Sanskrit is not as widely spoken as it once was, its influence can still be felt in all the other Indian languages that were derived from it.

C. Case for Sanskrit as the National Language in India

Sanskrit, often referred to as the “mother of all languages”, has a long and rich history in India. It is one of the oldest documented languages in the world and holds immense cultural and spiritual significance for the Indian people. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar (*The News Minute* and *The Hindu*), the father of India’s Constitution, was a strong advocate of Sanskrit being made the national language of India. He wanted Sanskrit to be used in official proceedings and declared it the Rastrabhasha, or national language, in the Constituent Assembly of India. However, Hindi eventually emerged victorious as a compromise between Hindi and English-speaking delegates in the Assembly. In recent times, a former Human Resource Development Minister has put forth his opinion for making Sanskrit an official language of India along with Hindi and English. His view was supported by Dr. Murali Manohar Joshi (ToI, 2016), who is also a seasoned Indian statesman and who wrote a recent opinion piece calling for Sanskrit to be given its due as an official language in India. However, no official steps have been taken yet to declare Sanskrit the national language of India or even make it an official language along with English and Hindi.

The Bharatiya Janata Party’s Member of Parliament, Nand Kumar Sai (Neha, 2022), had proposed a bill in the Lok Sabha in 2010 to make Sanskrit the national language of India. But it requires an amendment to the constitution, and the decision has not yet been taken. Congress leader Shashi Tharoor said he was in favour of making Sanskrit the official language of India, but only with consensus from all states. He also suggested that other languages should be given recognition as well, such as those spoken by scheduled tribes. He suggested language advice could be taken from experts to give the language its due status. Union Minister for Human Resource Development Prakash Javadekar (*India Times*) did not comment on making Sanskrit India’s national language but said that he welcomed any suggestion or decision that would promote it in any form. He also said that Devanagari script should be made available on computers and smart phones to encourage more people to learn and use it.

D. Scientific Importance of Sanskrit

Sanskrit holds scientific importance due to its linguistic structure, grammar, and phonetics, which make it a valuable language for various scientific disciplines. It possesses a highly organised and systematic linguistic structure with unambiguous grammar with precise rules governing sentence formation, word usage, and phonetics. This meticulous structure of Sanskrit serves as a reference point for linguistic research and comparative studies, aiding in understanding the evolution of languages and linguistic processes. It has a unique phonetic structure with a vast array of sounds and intricate pronunciation techniques. Its phonetic richness and accuracy make it an ideal language for studying phonetics, phonology, and sound patterns. This linguistic precision has contributed to the analysis and understanding of speech sounds, helping to develop phonetic systems and pronunciation guides in various scientific fields.

Sanskrit is known for its extensive vocabulary and word-formation capabilities. Its etymological system establishes detailed relationships between words, their roots, and their meanings. This makes Sanskrit valuable for etymological research and lexicography. The study of Sanskrit words and their origins aids in understanding the development, evolution, and interconnection of various languages, helping researchers uncover historical and linguistic connections. Not only this, but Sanskrit also has a close association with mathematics and science. Ancient mathematical treatises, such as the works of Aryabhata, Bhaskara, and Brahmagupta, were written in Sanskrit. The precise language and grammar of Sanskrit allowed for the clear and concise expression of mathematical concepts, making it easier to grasp complex mathematical ideas. Additionally, many scientific terms and concepts find their roots in Sanskrit, making it a valuable resource for scientific research and study.

Sanskrit texts contain extensive knowledge in the fields of astronomy and astrology. Ancient Indian astronomers, such as Aryabhata and Varahamihira, wrote treatises in Sanskrit describing astronomical observations, planetary movements, and celestial events. The precise language and technical vocabulary of Sanskrit allowed for accurate recording and transmission of this knowledge, providing a rich source for scientific exploration and historical understanding in these fields. The structured and rule-based nature of Sanskrit provides a foundation for computational linguistics, a subfield of artificial intelligence. The grammatical rules and syntax of Sanskrit are used to develop algorithms for natural language processing, machine translation, and language-based artificial intelligence systems. The logical and organised nature of the language makes Sanskrit a useful tool for analysing and modelling language patterns, aiding in the development of computational linguistics technologies. Thus, Sanskrit’s linguistic structure, phonetics, etymology, and links to mathematics, science, astronomy, and astrology justify its scientific importance. The precision and organisation of Sanskrit make it a valuable resource for diverse scientific disciplines, aiding in linguistic research, understanding sound patterns, etymological analysis, and studying ancient scientific knowledge.

E. Status of Sanskrit at International Level

Sanskrit is on the rise in European and non-European countries. Many universities have introduced Sanskrit faculty. There are students and teachers involved in the exchange of resources available in Sanskrit globally. As per the

information available on www.leverageedu.com, The UK, Ireland, Russia, Poland, and Germany are some of the top 5 countries where Sanskrit is very commonly celebrated.

1. **United Kingdom**– Sanskrit has become common in schools and universities in the UK. The St. James Jr. School promotes its use and some schools have made it compulsory as well.
2. **Ireland** shares a history with India regarding language. Old Irish and Sanskrit have some common words. Their language is as old as Sanskrit. Many schools have introduced Sanskrit into the curriculum, such as John Scottus School.
3. **Russia**—both Russian and Sanskrit share ancestry. It has a common grammatical base with Sanskrit, and both are pleasing to the ear.
4. **Poland**: Another country that has achieved a milestone in learning Sanskrit is Poland. Many Polish scholars have contributed to the Sanskrit department at the University of Calicut. The Indian students at Polish universities have also established their education in Sanskrit.
5. **Germany**– The common ground for both Indian and German students to learn Sanskrit with ease is Germany. Heidelberg University has Sanskrit teaching centres. The best 14 universities in Germany teach Sanskrit and Indian studies.
6. The institutes abroad providing Sanskrit education are listed below:
 - 1) Brown University – classics department
 - 2) California Institute of integral studies – Asian and comparative studies
 - 3) Columbia University – Department of middle east and Asian languages and cultures
 - 4) Cornell University – South Asia program
 - 5) John Hopkins University – language teaching Centre
 - 6) Harvard University– Sanskrit and Indians studies
 - 7) University of Iowa – Department of Asian languages and literature
 - 8) University of Queensland – Centre for Buddhist studies
 - 9) University of Sydney – Indian studies
 - 10) University of Copenhagen – Asian studies
 - 11) University of Helsinki – Institute for Asian and African studies
 - 12) Bonn University – Indian studies
 - 13) Hamburg University – Indian and Tibetan studies
 - 14) London University – Oriental and African studies
 - 15) University of Rome
 - 16) Oslo University
 - 17) Stockholm University
 - 18) Beijing University

Section – IV

NEP 2020: An Overview Related to Language Related Components

Among highlights of the new education policy 2020 is the decision to make mother tongue as the medium of instruction up to Fifth Class. It may also create a profound effect on the ongoing process of human resource development and to help students establish social and cultural relationships with the environment they are living in linguistic diversity of India necessitates linguistic diversity in schools too and in this regard, schools can play an important role in sustaining multilingualism in India. Therefore, the relatively high thrust that New Education Policy (NEP) gives on languages in schools does not require any justification. In doing so, the NEP 2020 has also amply focused the promotion of all Indian languages and mother tongues irrespective of their status. For the same reason, NEP recommends development of skilled teachers through four-year integrated B.Ed. Programmes.

NEP 2020 emphasizes the continuation of the three-language formula in schools and teaching-learning in bilingual and trilingual format. It also lays emphasis on skill development of teachers and educators by the use of modern technology for enhancing learning outcomes and making learning enjoyable. A provision is to be made for the teaching and learning of classical languages. It recommends the preparation of high-quality bilingual textbooks in Indian languages while offering courses in foreign languages as well. The futuristic education policy focuses on the need of preparation of innovative pedagogical materials and promotion of online language courses for various levels. It stresses on offering language diploma courses for in-service/prospective school teachers and promoting implementation of three-language formula. As a step in sustaining the changes, the new(recent) education policy recommends the preparation of basic grammar etc. taking into cognizance the requirements of various mother tongues including lesser known and tribal languages along with the task of developing children's materials bank and coordinating the establishment of language centres. In achieving the desired result, it also emphasises the need of coordination with state governments and publishers of children's literature.

Taking a digression, it is important to note that meticulous efforts are taken in this direction by various bodies. For instance, moving a step ahead towards the successful implementation of **NEP-2020** in terms of promotion of

regional languages in schools, Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti (NVS) has collaborated with National Testing Service-India (NTS-I) under Central Institute of Indian Languages (CIIL), Mysuru, for training NVS language teachers by offering a six-day online capacity building programme for each language. NVS in collaboration with CIIL wishes to run this programme for 14 languages in total. In this connection, capacity-building programmes for 4 languages — Kannada, Marathi, Malayalam and Telugu.

In conclusion, NEP recommends the teaching of Indian languages with English and Foreign Languages. NEP envisages the promotion of Indian languages through regular use, preparation of pedagogical materials, training of teachers, adoption of mother tongues as medium of instruction, innovative methods, judicious use of technology and development of positive attitude towards all languages and their remarkable unity. NEP also recommends of linguistic empowerment of hearing-impaired population through teaching of Indian Sign Language with its local varieties. Thus, after a careful analysis, none can deny the objectives of NEP2020 are directed towards establishing or perhaps reestablishing the identity of India as a strong nation empowered in all aspects and prepared to bear the testimony of Indian ethos and ideals.

Section – V

A. Findings

- The use of the mother tongue in education enhances critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and overall academic achievement. The mother tongue serves as a foundation for learning additional languages. Proficiency in one's mother tongue can facilitate the acquisition of other languages, as it provides a cognitive framework and linguistic awareness.
- In conclusion, regional and local languages hold immense significance in India. They serve as vital vehicles for cultural preservation, identity formation, inclusivity, and efficient communication. Embracing and promoting these languages is crucial for celebrating India's linguistic diversity and ensuring the holistic development of its diverse communities. This can be achieved through educational initiatives, governmental support, media representation, and societal acknowledgment of the importance of regional and local languages as invaluable assets for the nation.
- Hindi is widely regarded as the primary language for over 180 million individuals, serving as their mother tongue. Additionally, it has the status of being the secondary language for approximately 500 million individuals. Hindi was employed by Mahatma Gandhi as a means to foster national cohesion in India, thereby earning it the epithet "Language of Unity".
- With 584.57 million native speakers, Hindi has the highest prevalence in India. A total of about 585.5 million people worldwide speak Hindi as their mother tongue. (worlddata.info) Thus, equally convincing is the position of Hindi as the national and official language of India.
- Sanskrit is deeply ingrained in Indian culture and heritage. It is the language of ancient Indian scriptures, including the Vedas, Upanishads, and Bhagavad Gita. These texts, which contain profound philosophical and spiritual teachings, are considered the foundation of Indian spirituality and provide valuable insights into the country's cultural traditions. By making Sanskrit the national language, India can strengthen its connection with its rich cultural past and preserve this heritage for future generations.
- India is a linguistically diverse country, with hundreds of languages and dialects spoken across its regions. Adopting Sanskrit as the national language can act as a unifying force. Sanskrit, being a classical language, is not associated with any particular region or community. It belongs to all Indians, regardless of their mother tongue. By promoting Sanskrit, India can foster a sense of linguistic unity and overcome language barriers, facilitating better communication and understanding between different states and regions.
- Sanskrit is highly valued in the fields of education and research. It serves as the foundation for many Indian languages and contributes to the development of linguistic skills. Studying Sanskrit enhances memory, analytical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Additionally, many scientific and mathematical concepts were originally expressed in Sanskrit, making it an essential language for research and scientific endeavours. Making Sanskrit the national language would give it the recognition it deserves, encouraging more educational institutions to teach and promote the language.
- Sanskrit not only holds immense religious and spiritual value but also houses a vast body of knowledge in various academic disciplines. Making Sanskrit the national language would help revive and preserve this ancient wisdom. It would encourage the translation and study of Sanskrit texts, ensuring their accessibility for future generations. By doing so, India can safeguard its intellectual heritage and disseminate the invaluable knowledge contained within Sanskrit texts.

- Sanskrit has a global influence beyond India's borders. Many scientific and academic institutions around the world study Sanskrit texts for their profound knowledge and linguistic complexity. By elevating Sanskrit to the status of a national language, India can position itself as a centre for Sanskrit studies and research, attracting scholars and researchers from across the globe. This can contribute to India's soft power and promote cultural exchange and collaboration on an international level.

B. Conclusion

In conclusion, the promotion of mother tongues and local languages is essential for the preservation of cultural heritage, while the adoption of a formal national language should be done in a manner that respects linguistic diversity and promotes inclusivity. A comprehensive language policy that strikes a balance between regional languages and a common language can contribute to a harmonious and united society. Hindi, as the language spoken by almost 50% of the total population, and Sanskrit, owing to its historical significance and its role in preserving ancient wisdom, all make a compelling case for considering them as the Indian national languages. Embracing Sanskrit would strengthen India's cultural identity, foster unity, promote education, and elevate the country's stature on the global stage.

C. Recommendation

The promotion of mother tongues and local languages is crucial for preserving cultural diversity, fostering inclusivity, and ensuring effective communication within communities. These languages carry the collective identity, history, and wisdom of a particular region or community. While it is important to recognise and promote the significance of mother tongues and local languages, the adoption of Sanskrit as the formal national language of Bhaarat poses both challenges and opportunities. Hindi has already established its imprint on the minds of Indians across the globe and thus deserves to retain the status it holds. Likewise, Sanskrit has historical and cultural importance in India, being the root of many Indian languages and the language of ancient texts. However, any decision regarding a national language should be made with careful consideration of practicality, inclusivity, and linguistic diversity. In case the change is perceived to be challenging, then the implementation bodies should devise systematic, staggered phase-wise adoption. Language policies should aim to empower individuals to communicate effectively in their mother tongue while also equipping them with proficiency in a common language for national integration.

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